

Electron Affinity of Iodine and Ionisation Potentials of some Thioureas from Charge Transfer Band Maxima

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From CT-band maxima of the complexes of molecular iodine with several thioureas ionisation potentials of the donors determined by a comparative method agree closely with the values computed theoretically by HMO treatment. The electron affinity of iodine calculated by several procedures agrees well with the literature data.

WITH molecular iodine thioureas form n-donor- σ -acceptor type of 1:1 complexes of high thermodynamic stability and large b^2/a^2 values¹. In these complexes sulphur with nearly p_y orbital is believed to be the donor site^{2,3}, and the lone pair electrons on the nitrogen atoms play a minor role as donor towards iodine⁴. Recently Abdel-Mottaleb *et al.*⁵ emphasised the role of CS π -electrons of thioureas in studying their donor properties. These authors have studied CT complexes of several thioureas with iodine and have calculated the ionisation potentials of donors (I_D) from simple HMO treatment. Although several studies of CT complexes between iodine and thioureas^{1,3-5} have been done, previously no attempt has been made to calculate the ionisation potential values of thioureas from the experimental CT band maxima. In the present study we have determined the I_D values of several thioureas from CT transition energy of their complexes with iodine by a comparative method. Incidentally the electron affinity (E_A) of iodine has also been calculated from the same data. The present paper reports the results of our work in this line.

Principle :

I_D values may be calculated from relation (1).

$$I_{D(TU \text{ or } RTU)} = (h\nu_{CT})_{(TU \text{ or } RTU-I_2)} - (h\nu_{CT})_{BZ-I_2} + \Delta_{(TU \text{ or } RTU-I_2)} - \Delta_{BZ-I_2} + I_{D(BZ)} \quad (1)$$

where $h\nu_{CT}$ refers to the CT transition energy and Δ is the stabilisation energy of the complex. The subscript BZ means benzene and BZ- I_2 refers to the benzene-iodine complex, while TU or RTU- I_2 refers to thiourea or substituted thiourea-iodine complex.

The stabilisation energy, Δ , is given by equation^{6,7} (2).

$$\Delta = W_1 - W_0 \quad (2)$$

$$\text{where, } W_1 = W_E - R_E \quad (3)$$

$$W_0 = W_G - R_G = \Delta H - R_G \quad (4)$$

$$W_E = W_G + h\nu = \Delta H + h\nu \quad (5)$$

$$R_G = \frac{1}{2} \{ (S^2 h\nu - 2\beta_G S - h\nu) + [(S^2 h\nu - 2\beta_G S - h\nu)^2 - 4\beta_G^2]^{1/2} \} \quad (6)$$

$$R_E = \beta_E^2 / (W_E - W_0) \quad (7)$$

$$\beta_G = [(a^*S - b^*)ah\nu] / (aa^* + bb^*) \quad (8)$$

$$\beta_E = \beta_G - Sh\nu \quad (9)$$

$$(a^*b - ab^*) = (bb^* - aa^*)S \quad (10)$$

W_0 , W_1 , W_G and W_E refer to the energies of the no-bond, dative, ground and excited states of the CT complex, respectively. The resonance energies of the ground and excited states of the complex are denoted by R_G and R_E , respectively; a and b are the contributions of the no-bond and dative forms in the ground state of the complex, while in the excited state of the same the respective contributions are b^* and a^* . β_G and β_E represent the two quantities ($W_{01} - W_G S$) and ($W_{01} - W_E S$), respectively. S is the overlap integral, ΔH - the heat of reaction and $h\nu = h\nu_{CT}$.

The electron affinity (E_A) of iodine may be calculated from equation⁸ (11).

$$\frac{b}{a} = \frac{-W_{O1} - W_0 S}{I_D - E_A - C} \quad (11)$$

where, $W_{O1} = \int \Psi_0 H \Psi_1 d\tau$, and C is a coulomb energy term. b/a is calculated from equation⁹ (12).

$$b^2/a^2 = \Delta H/h\nu_{CT} \quad (12)$$

Equation (11) on rearrangement yields

$$I_D = -(W_{O1} + W_0 S) a/b + (E_A + C) \quad (13)$$

according to which a plot of I_D vs a/b should be a straight line with intercept equal to $(E_A + C)$ from which E_A can be evaluated.

Alternatively, E_A can be calculated from the intercept $(=E_A + \Delta)$ of the linear plot of $h\nu_{CT}$ vs I_D according to equation¹⁰ (14).

$$h\nu_{CT} = I_D - (E_A + \Delta) \quad (14)$$

Results and Discussion

I_D values of a number of thioureas, such as thiourea (TU), phenylthiourea (PTU), diphenylthiourea (DPTU), benzylthiourea (BTU), dibenzylthiourea (DBTU) and tetramethylthiourea (TMTU) have been calculated by using equation (1). In all calculations, we have used the data of Abdel-Mottaleb *et al.*⁴. For calculating the stabilisation energy of thiourea-iodine complexes the overlap integral, S has been assigned a value of 0.3 in view of the strong nature of the complexes^{1,7}. The other relevant data^{1,2} including I_D values are shown in Table 1. It is seen that the ionisation potentials of thioureas calculated by equation (1) agree closely with those computed theoretically by HMO treatment⁴. Further, except DPTU the values are in the same order as those of Abdel-Mottaleb *et al.*⁴.

according to the latter the CT-band maximum of PTU- I_2 complex appears at 302 nm. Using 302 nm value $I_{D(PTU)}$ has been calculated to be 8.44 eV instead of 8.62 eV, and the former agrees closely with the HMO value of 8.46 eV.

The first ionisation potential of TMTU determined by electron impact method is 8.12 eV which compares favourably with the value 7.86 eV calculated by the comparative method than 7.62 eV calculated by HMO treatment⁴.

The electron affinity of iodine has been calculated separately from the value of b/a of each thiourea- I_2 complex using equation (11). The average $E_{A(I_2)}$ is 1.83 eV. Alternatively, $E_{A(I_2)}$ evaluated from the intercept of the best straight line of the

Fig. 1

TABLE 1

System	$h\nu_{CT}$ eV	$-\Delta H$ eV	b^2/a^2	Δ^* eV	I_D (eV)		$E_{A(I_2)}$ eV
					(Comparative method)	(Theoretical)	
DPTU	4.22	0.45	0.102	2.68	8.64	8.36	
PTU	4.19	0.45	0.107	2.64	8.62	8.46	1.83 ^a
TU	4.16	0.42	0.104	2.65	8.63	8.58	1.60 ^b
BTU	4.08	0.47	0.115	2.54	8.49	8.45	0.85 ^c
DBTU	3.94	0.41	0.105	2.47	8.32	8.36	
TMTU	3.71	0.41	0.111	2.34	7.86	7.62	

* 2.55 average. ^aEquation (11); ^bGraphical, equation (13); ^cGraphical, equation (14). $h\nu_{CT(BZ-I_2)} = 4.18$ eV, $\Delta_{BZ-I_2} = 3.25$ eV, and $I_{D(BZ)} = 9.24$ eV (all Ref. 11).

There are some discrepancies in the reported values of λ_{max} of PTU- I_2 complex between the works of Abdel-Mottaleb *et al.* and that of Shah and Murty⁵. While the former reported a value of 296nm,

plot of I_D vs a/b (Fig. 1, a) according to equation (13) is 1.6 eV. The value of C required in this calculation has been taken⁸ 3.3 eV. These electron affinity values are close to Person's^{1,2} value of 1.7 eV as the

electron affinity of iodine. From the intercept, $E_A + \Delta$, of the linear plot of $h\nu_{CT}$ vs I_D (Fig. 1, b) of thiourea-iodine complexes $E_{A(I_2)}$ value comes out to be 0.85 eV which, although much lower than Person's value, agrees with Briegleb and Czekalla's¹³ value of 0.81 eV. The Δ value required in this calculation is an average one and has been taken as 2.55 eV.

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